

2020-04-29

Subject: Literature list on the outputs of COST Action Mining the European Anthroposphere

The “Mining the European Anthroposphere” (MINEA) is a pan-European expert network, which received funding from the COST Association between 2016 and 2020. The network pools knowledge for estimating the future recoverability of raw materials from anthropogenic resources.

This document provides references on deliverables, scientific articles, conference and workshop proceedings, book sections, working papers, STSM reports, presentations and posters and MINEA events and presentations and posters at non-MINEA events.

The references have been provided by MINEA Working Group members.

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1 Deliverables

Year 2018: [1-4]
Year 2020: [5-7]

1. Saez, P., Osmani, M. and Vitale, P. (2018). Recovery technologies for construction and demolition waste. Mining the European Anthroposphere (MINEA). online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3760465>.
2. Krook, J., Cleall, P., Rosendal, R. and Carvalho, T. (2018). Recovery technologies for waste in landfills. MINEA Deliverable. Mining the European Anthroposphere (MINEA). online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3768961>.

3. Leder, J., Syc, M., Biganzoli, L., Bogush, A., Bontempi, E., Braga, R., Costa, G., Funari, V., Grosso, M., Hyks, J., Kameníková, P., Quina, M., Rasmussen, E., Schlumberger, S., Simon, F.-G., and Weibel, G. (2018). Recovery technologies for waste incineration residues (MINEA Deliverable). Mining the European Anthroposphere (MINEA). online: <http://www.minea-network.eu/upload/D31Report.pdf>.
4. Heiberg, S., Heuss-Aßbichler, S., Hilton, J., Horváth, Z., Kral, U., Krook, J., Laner, D., Müller, F., Mueller, S., Mohamed, O., Stegemann, J., Wäger, P., Winterstetter, A., and Wittmer, D. (2018). Specifications to apply the UNFC to Anthropogenic Resources. United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE). Geneva. online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3759026>.
5. Blasenbauer, D., Bogush, A., Carvalho, T., Cleall, P., Cormio, C., Guglietta, D., Fellner, J., Fernández-Alonso, M., Heuss-Aßbichler, S., Huber, F., Kral, U., Kriipsalu, M., Krook, J., Laner, D., Lederer, J., Lemièrre, B., Liu, G., Mao, R., Mueller, S., Quina, M., Sinnett, D., Stegemann, J., Syc, M., Szabó, K., Werner, T.T., Wille, E., Winterstetter, A., and Žibret, G. (2020). Knowledge base to facilitate anthropogenic resource assessment (MINEA Deliverable). COST Action Mining the European Anthroposphere (MINEA). online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3739164>.
6. Heuss-Aßbichler, S., Horváth, Z., Kral, U., Løvik, A., Mueller, S., Simoni, M., Stegemann, J., Wäger, P., and Winterstetter, A. (2020). Strategic roadmap on Sustainable Management of Anthropogenic Resources (MINEA Deliverable). COST Action Mining the European Anthroposphere (MINEA). online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3739269>.
7. Kral, U., Heuss-Aßbichler, S. and Simoni, M. (2020). Anthropogenic Resource Classification. Mining the European Anthroposphere (MINEA). online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3751219>.

2 Scientific Articles

This list contains articles that

- are on topic of MINEA
- that are co-authored by at least two MINEA participants from two countries participating in MINEA, and
- for which the networking activity was necessary.

Year 2016: [1]

Year 2017: [2-6]

Year 2018: [7-13]

Year 2019: [14-19]

Year 2020: [20-25]

1. Laner, D., Cencic, O., Svensson, N. and Krook, J. (2016). *Quantitative Analysis of Critical Factors for the Climate Impact of Landfill Mining*. Environ Sci Technol. 50(13): p. 6882-91. online: <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.6b01275>.
2. Benassi, L., Dalipi, R., Consigli, V., Pasquali, M., Borgese, L., Depero, L.E., Clegg, F., Bingham, P.A., and Bontempi, E. (2017). *Integrated management of ash from industrial and domestic combustion: a new sustainable approach for reducing greenhouse gas emissions from energy conversion*. Environmental Science and Pollution Research. 24(17): p. 14834-14846. online: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-017-9037-y>.
3. Burlakovs, J., Kriipsalu, M., Klavins, M., Bhatnagar, A., Vincevica-Gaile, Z., Stenis, J., Jani, Y., Mykhaylenko, V., Denafas, G., Turkadze, T., Hogland, M., Rudovica, V., Kaczala, F., Rosendal, R.M., and Hogland, W. (2017). *Paradigms on landfill mining: From dump site scavenging to ecosystem services revitalization*. Resources, Conservation and Recycling. 123: p. 73-84. online: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2016.07.007>.
4. Jani, Y., Kriipsalu, M., Pehme, K.-M. and Burlakovs, J. (2017). *Composition of Waste at an Early EU-Landfill of Torma in Estonia*. Iranica Journal of Energy and Environment. 8(2): p. 113-117. online: <https://doi.org/10.5829/ijee.2017.08.02.03>.

5. Bhatnagar, A., Kaczala, F., Burlakovs, J., Kriipsalu, M., Hogland, M. and Hogland, W. (2017). *Hunting for valuables from landfills and assessing their market opportunities A case study with Kudjape landfill in Estonia*. Waste Management & Research. 35(6): p. 627-635. online: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242x17697816>.
6. Kaczala, F., Mehdinejad, M.H., Lääne, A., Orupõld, K., Bhatnagar, A., Kriipsalu, M., and Hogland, W. (2017). *Leaching characteristics of the fine fraction from an excavated landfill: physico-chemical characterization*. Journal of Material Cycles and Waste Management. 19(1): p. 294-304. online: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10163-015-0418-3>.
7. Quina, M., Bontempi, E., Bogush, A., Schlumberger, S., Weibel, G., Braga, R., Funari, V., Hyks, J., Rasmussen, E., and Leder, J. (2018). *Technologies for the management of MSW incineration ashes from gas cleaning: new perspectives on recovery of secondary raw materials and circular economy*. Science of The Total Environment. 635: p. 526-542. online: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.04.150>.
8. Mrkajić, V., Stanisavljevic, N., Wang, X., Tomas, L. and Haro, P. (2018). *Efficiency of packaging waste management in a European Union candidate country*. Resources, Conservation and Recycling. 136: p. 130-141. online: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2018.04.008>.
9. Huber, F., Herzel, H., Adam, C., Mallow, O., Blasenbauer, D. and Fellner, J. (2018). *Combined disc pelletisation and thermal treatment of MSWI fly ash*. Waste Management. 73: p. 381-391. online: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2017.12.020>.
10. Winterstetter, A., Wille, E., Nagels, P. and Fellner, J. (2018). *Decision making guidelines for mining historic landfill sites in Flanders*. Waste Manag. 77: p. 225-237. online: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2018.03.049>.
11. Burlakovs, J., Jani, Y., Kriipsalu, M., Vincevica-Gaile, Z., Kaczala, F., Celma, G., Ozola, R., Rozina, L., Rudovica, V., Hogland, M., Viksna, A., Pehme, K.-M., Hogland, W., and Klavins, M. (2018). *On the way to 'zero waste' management: Recovery potential of elements, including rare earth elements, from fine fraction of waste*. Journal of Cleaner Production. 186: p. 81-90. online: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.03.102>.
12. Hogland, M., Āriņa, D., Kriipsalu, M., Jani, Y., Kaczala, F., de Sá Salomão, A.L., Orupõld, K., Pehme, K.-M., Rudoviča, V., Denafas, G., Burlakovs, J., Vincēviča-Gaile, Z., and Hogland, W. (2018). *Remarks on four novel landfill mining case studies in Estonia and Sweden*. Journal of Material Cycles and Waste Management. 20(2): p. 1355-1363. online: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10163-017-0683-4>.
13. Bučinskas, A., Kriipsalu, M. and Denafas, G. (2018). *Proposal for Feasibility Assessment Model for Landfill Mining and Its Implementation for Energy Generation Scenarios*. Sustainability. 10(8). online: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10082882>.
14. Villoria Sáez, P. and Osmani, M. (2019). *A diagnosis of construction and demolition waste generation and recovery practice in the European Union*. Journal of Cleaner Production. 241: p. 118400. online: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.118400>.
15. Laner, D., Esguerra, J.L., Krook, J., Horttanainen, M., Kriipsalu, M., Rosendal, R.M., and Stanisavljevic, N. (2019). *Systematic assessment of critical factors for the economic performance of landfill mining in Europe: What drives the economy of landfill mining?* Waste Manag. 95: p. 674-686. online: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2019.07.007>.
16. Mutafela, R.N., Marques, M., Jani, Y., Kriipsalu, M. and Hogland, W. (2019). *Physico-chemical characteristics of fine fraction materials from an old crystal glass dumpsite in Sweden*. Chemistry and Ecology. 35(9): p. 877-890. online: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02757540.2019.1648442>.
17. Burlakovs, J., Kriipsalu, M., Porshnov, D., Jani, Y., Ozols, V., Pehme, K.M., Rudovica, V., Grinfelde, I., Pilecka, J., Vincevica-Gaile, Z., Turkadze, T., Hogland, W., and Klavins, M. (2019). *Gateway of Landfilled Plastic Waste Towards Circular Economy in Europe*. Separations. 6(2). online: <https://doi.org/10.3390/separations6020025>.

18. Giro-Paloma, J., Mañosa, J., Maldonado-Alameda, A., Quina, M.J. and Chimenos, J.M. (2019). *Rapid sintering of weathered municipal solid waste incinerator bottom ash and rice husk for lightweight aggregate manufacturing and product properties*. Journal of Cleaner Production. 232: p. 713-721. online: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.06.010>.
19. Lanau, M., Liu, G., Kral, U., Wiedenhofer, D., Keijzer, E., Yu, C., and Ehlert, C. (2019). *Taking Stock of Built Environment Stock Studies: Progress and Prospects*. Environ Sci Technol. 53(15): p. 8499-8515. online: <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.8b06652>.
20. Blasenbauer, D., Huber, F., Lederer, J., Quina, M.J., Blanc-Biscarat, D., Bogush, A., Bontempi, E., Blondeau, J., Chimenos, J.M., Dahlbo, H., Fagerqvist, J., Giro-Paloma, J., Hjelm, O., Hyks, J., Keaney, J., Lupsea-Toader, M., O'Caollai, C.J., Orupöld, K., Pająk, T., Simon, F.-G., Svecova, L., Šyc, M., Ulvang, R., Vaajasaari, K., Van Caneghem, J., van Zomeren, A., Vasarevičius, S., Wégner, K., and Fellner, J. (2020). *Legal situation and current practice of waste incineration bottom ash utilisation in Europe*. Waste Management. 102: p. 868-883. online: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2019.11.031>.
21. Šyc, M., Simon, F.G., Hyks, J., Braga, R., Biganzoli, L., Costa, G., Funari, V., and Grosso, M. (2020). *Metal recovery from incineration bottom ash: state-of-the-art and recent developments*. Journal of Hazardous Materials. p. 122433. online: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2020.122433>.
22. Mueller, S.R., Kral, U. and Wäger, P.A. (2020). *Developing material recovery projects: Lessons learned from processing municipal solid waste incineration residues*. Journal of Cleaner Production. 259. online: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120490>.
23. Gomes, H.I., Funari, V. and Ferrari, R. (2020). *Bioleaching for resource recovery from low-grade wastes like fly and bottom ashes from municipal incinerators: A SWOT analysis*. Science of The Total Environment. 715: p. 136945. online: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.136945>.
24. Gomes, H.I., Funari, V., Dinelli, E. and Soavi, F. (2020). *Enhanced electrochemical bioleaching of fly ashes of municipal solid waste incineration for metal recovery*. Electrochimica Acta. p. 136188. online: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2020.136188>.
25. Žibret, G., Lemièrre, B., Mendez, A.M., Cormio, C., Sinnett, D., Cleall, P., Szabo, K., and Carvalho, T. *National mineral waste databases as an information source for assessing material recovery potential from mine waste, tailings and metallurgical waste*. Manuscript submitted to Minerals, MDPI.

3 Conference & Workshop Proceedings

Year 2016: [1-4]

Year 2020: [5]

1. Simoni, M., Heuss-Aßbichler, S. and Kral, U. (2016). *Workshop on "Opportunities and Challenges for the Classification & Reporting of Anthropogenic Resources" (Book of Abstracts)*. In: Proceedings of the. COST Action Mining the European Anthroposphere. online: http://www.minea-network.eu/upload/1_BookofAbstracts.pdf.
2. Osmani, M. and Kral, U. (2016). *COST Action MINEA Workshop Proceedings on Recovery technologies for construction and demolition waste*. 16.-17. November 2017.
3. Krook, J., Kral, U. and Carvalho, T. (2016). *COST Action MINEA Workshop Proceedings on Technologies for material recovery from landfills and mining residues*. 23.-24. September 2016.
4. Lederer, J. and Šyc, M. (2016). *COST Action MINEA Workshop Proceedings on Technologies and data for material recovery from waste incineration residues in Europe*. 19.-20. October 2016.
5. Focaccia, S., Kral, U., Cormio, C. and Hengl, I. (2020). *Book of Abstract. Poster session at Conference on Mining the European Anthroposphere, 20-21 Feb 2020, Bologna*. Bologna. Bologna. p. 43 Seiten. online: <http://katalog.ub.tuwien.ac.at/AC15607338>.

4 Book sections

Year 2019: [1]

1. Osmani, M. and Villoria-Sáez, P. (2019). *Current and emerging construction waste management trends and approaches*, in *Waste: A Handbook for Management*, T.M. Letcher and D.A. Vallero, (Editors). Academic Press.

5 Working Papers

Year 2018: [1]

1. Kral, U., Fellner, J., Heuss-Abichler, S., Laner, D., Müller, F., Simoni, M., Rechberger, H., Weber, L., Wellmer, F.-W., and Winterstetter, A. (2018). *Vorratsklassifikation von anthropogenen Ressourcen: Historischer Kontext, Kurzvorstellung und Ausblick*. Wien, München, Trondheim, Hannover, Mol, Antwerpen. p. 13. online: <http://resolver.obvsg.at/urn:nbn:at:at-ubtuw:3-3672>.

6 STSM reports

MINEA members have been on Short-Term-Scientific Missions (STSM) abroad. The STSM reports are not public available, but can be retrieved on personal request.

Year 2016: [1-3]

Year 2017: [4-10]

Year 2018: [11-15]

Year 2019: [16-26]

Year 2020: [27, 28]

1. Pierluca, V. (2016). Overview on construction & demolition waste recycling technologies.
2. Simoni, M. (2016). Opportunities and Challenges for the Classification & Reporting of Anthropogenic Resources
3. Álvarez, M. (2016). Technologies for material recovery from landfills and mining residues.
4. Bogush, A. (2017). Recovery technologies and utilization of waste incineration residues.
5. Huber, F. (2017). Thermal treatment of pelletised MSWI fly ash.
6. Miekley, B. (2017). Contribution to a critical review on built environment stock studies.
7. Esguerra, J.L. (2017). Extensive literature review of previous economic assessments of landfill mining and landfill management projects including the categorization of identified critical factors and its consequent uncertainty handling.
8. Einhüpl, P. (2017). Mapping of societal and environmental impacts of LFM.
9. Szabó, K. (2017). Visit at the Geological Survey of Finland.
10. Seniūnaitė, J. (2017). Research of short-term natural weathering MSWI bottom ash properties.
11. Saez, P. (2018). Technologies for Recovering Materials from Construction and Demolition Waste.

12. Mueller, S. (2018). Resource Assessment of Municipal Solid Waste Streams: Testing The Applicability of the United Nations Framework Classification and its Specification for Anthropogenic Resources.
13. Gontia, P. (2018). Material composition database of buildings in the nord European context.
14. Blasenbauer, D. (2018). Legal situation on utilisation and disposal of municipal solid waste (MSW) incineration bottom ash in Europe.
15. Bimesmeier, T. (2018). Towards a knowledge base for material reserves and resources in buildings & infrastructures.
16. Fidanchevski, E. (2019). Valorisation of industrial residues for synthesis of innovative mineral binders.
17. Maldonado, A. (2019). Thermo-physical characterization of lightweight aggregates by using municipal solid waste incineration bottom ash.
18. Chimenos-Ribera, J. (2019). Thermophysical characterisation of lightweight aggregates formulated by using municipal solid waste incineration bottom ash.
19. Korotenko, E. (2019). Treatment of bottom ash fractions for construction industry utilization.
20. Angjusheva, B. (2019). Characterisation of the C&DW and determination of the properties of ceramics obtained from C&DW and clay.
21. Lanau, M. (2019). Towards a knowledge base: Development of an urban material stocks data structure and database.
22. Havukainen, J. (2019). Quantitative assessment of environmental impacts of waste recovery possibilities using combinatorial algorithms and Monte Carlo Simulation.
23. Gomes, H. (2019). Bioleaching and resource recovery from Municipal Solid Waste Incineration ashes
24. Bandarra, B. (2019). Studies on ecotoxicological tests for incineration bottom ash classification.
25. Cormio, C. (2019). A knowledge base for the assessment of secondary raw materials recoverability from Mining residues. Approaches and case studies.
26. Mao, R. (2019). Modelling urban metabolism for urban sustainability.
27. Giorgi, S. (2020). Enablers and barriers of reuse/recycling of building and demolition waste.
28. Alonso, M. (2020). Creation of European projects database as a methodological guide for approachable secondary raw materials case studies.

7 Presentations and posters at MINEA events

You find the information on the MINEA webpage (<http://www.minea-network.eu/events>) and the MINEA Final Conference webpage (<http://conference.minea-network.eu/>). If material for a meeting is missing, please text a message (info@minea-network.eu).

8 Presentations and posters at non-MINEA events

It is noted that some presentations and posters are associated with articles in proceedings.

Year 2016: [1-4]
Year 2017: [5-24]
Year 2018: [25-62]
Year 2019: [63-69]

Year 2020: [70]

1. Winterstetter, A., Laner, D., Wille, E., Nagels, P., Rechberger, H. and Fellner, J. (2016). *Development of a resource classification framework for old landfills in Flanders (Project RECLAF)*. Conference paper and oral presentation. 3rd Symposium on Urban Mining (SUM2016). 23 - 25 May 2016, Bergamo, Italy. online: https://publik.tuwien.ac.at/files/PubDat_250311.pdf.
2. Denafas, G., Bučinskas, A., Burlakovs, J., Dace, E., Baziene, K., Horttanainen, M., Havukainen, J., Kaartinen, T., Rosendal, R.M., Kriipsalu, M., Jani, Y., and Hogland, W. (2016). *Investigation for landfill mining feasibilities in the Nordic and Baltic EU countries: overview of project results*. Conference paper and oral presentation. 4th International Conference on Sustainable Solid Waste Management. 23.-25. June 2016, Limassol, Cyprus.
3. Kral, U. (2016). *Cost Action: Mining the European Anthroposphere*. Oral presentation. ISWA World Congress 2016, 19.-23. September 2016.
4. Rosendal, R.M. (2016). *The important role of landfills in the circular economy*. Conference paper and oral presentation. Linnaeus Eco-tech 16. 21.-23. November 2016, Kalmar, Sweden.
5. Kral, U. (2017). *UNFC as an enabler for management of anthropogenic resources*. Oral presentation. EFG/UNECE conference: International cooperation on natural resources, 9.-10. February 2017.
6. Heuss-Aßbichler, S. (2017). *Classifying Anthropogenic resources and managing secondary raw materials*. Oral presentation. World Resources Forum 2017, 24.-25. October 2017.
7. Kral, U. (2017). *COST Action MINEA and its relevance for SCRREEN*. Oral presentation. SCRREEN Clustering Meeting, 28. June 2017.
8. Kral, U., Heuss-Aßbichler, S., Simoni, M. and Rechberger, H. (2017). *Resource potentials in residues and the need for a global classification standard*. Oral presentation. International Workshop on Waste Prevention & 3R Strategy 2017, 23.-24. October 2017.
9. Kral, U., Lederer, J. and Fellner, J. (2017). *UNFC for the recovery of energy & materials from waste*. Oral presentation. 26th UNECE Committee on Sustainable Energy Session, 27. September 2017.
10. Lederer, J., Šyc, M., Bogush, A. and Fellner, J. (2017). *A network approach towards a secondary raw material inventory for Europe applied to waste incineration residues*. Conference paper and oral presentation. 16th International Waste Management and Landfill Symposium, R. Cossu and J. Stegemann (Editors). 2.-6. October 2017, Forte Village, Santa Margherita die Pula.
11. Mueller, S.R. (2017). *Mining the European Anthroposphere (MINEA): Classification and reporting of material resources/reserves (Poster)*. Oral presentation. World Resources Forum 2017, 24.-25. October 2017.
12. Simoni, M. (2017). *Primary versus secondary mineral materials – Can recycling replace mining?* Conference poster. NTNU Sustainability Science Conference: Transition to sustainable systems, 18.-20. October 2017, Trondheim, Norway.
13. Winterstetter, A. (2017). *A Resource Classification Framework for historic Landfills in Flanders*. Oral presentation. ISWA World Congress & WASTECON® 2017, 25.-27. September 2017.
14. Rosendal, R.M. and Hjelmar, O. (2017). *Sorting and separation of landfilled non-hazardous waste at five danish landfills*. Conference paper and oral presentation. Sardinia 2017 Symposium. 2.-6. October 2017, Forte Village S. Margherita di Pula, Italy.
15. Rosendal, R., Christensen, J.M., Reimann, P., Nielsen, S., Sundberg, P., Felding, H., Overgaard, L.B., and Poulsen, S. (2017). *Landfill mining demonstration project at Skarup Landfill, Denmark*. Conference paper and oral presentation. Sardinia 2017 Symposium. 2.-6. October 2017, Forte Village, S. Margherita Di Pula, Italy.

16. Petrovska, S., Fidancevska, M. and Angjusheva, B. (2017). *Production and Characterisation of Ceramics from Clay and Construction & Demolition waste*. Conference paper and oral presentation. 1st International Students Scientific Conference “Multidisciplinary Approach to Contemporary Research”. 25.-26. November 2017, Belgrade, Serbia.
17. Levkovski, N., Iloski, L. and Angjusheva, B. (2017). *Optimization of the Main Process Parameters of Ceramics produced from Clay and Demolition Waste*. Conference paper and oral presentation. 1st International Students Scientific Conference “Multidisciplinary Approach to Contemporary Research”. 25.-26. November 2017, Belgrade, Serbia.
18. Petrovska, S., Fidancevska, M. and Angjusheva, B. (2017). *Re-Use of Construction and Demolition Waste in Clay Based Ceramics*. Oral presentation. XII Students’ Congress of SCTM, 12.-14. October 2017.
19. Levkovski, N., Iloski, L. and Angjusheva, B. (2017). *Incorporation of the Construction and Demolition Waste in Ceramics: Optimization of the process parameters*. Oral presentation. XII Students’ Congress of SCTM, 12.-14. October 2017.
20. Salgın, B., Tıkansak Karadayı, T., Coşgun, N. and Aydın İpekçi, C. (2017). *Examining the Recovery Possibilities of C&D Wastes in Turkey*. Oral presentation. 23-25 October 2017, International Congress of Health and Environment: Adana, Turkey.
21. Clausen, A., Clausen, A., Kriipsalu, M. and Pretz, T. (2017). *MSW Management in Estonia: The current situation and future potential for energy recovery from sustainable sources*. Oral presentation. 16-18 May 2017, 7th International Symposium MBT, MRF & Recycling 2017, Waste-to-Resources 2017: Hanover, Germany.
22. Quina, M. (2017). *Recycling APC residues in lightweight aggregates*. Oral presentation. 30-31 May 2017, Workshop on “Technologies for Recovery of Secondary Raw Materials from Waste Incineration”: Bologna, Italy.
23. Quina, M. (2017). *Technologies for the management of MSW incineration ashes from gas cleaning and new perspectives on recovery of secondary raw materials*. Oral presentation. 30-31 May 2017, Bologna, Italy.
24. Leder, J., Bogush, A. and Fellner, J. (2017). *The utilization of solid residues from municipal solid waste incineration in the cement industry: A review*. Conference paper and oral presentation. 16th International Waste Management and Landfill Symposium, R. Cossu and R. Stegmann (Editors). 2-6 Oct. 2017.
25. Einhäupl, P., Krook, J., Svensson, N., van Acker, K. and van Passel, S. (2018). *Enhanced Landfill Mining at the REMO site: Stakeholders’ perspectives on implementation*. Conference paper and oral presentation. 4th International Symposium on Enhanced Landfill Mining, P.T. Jones and L. Machiels (Editors). 5.-6. February 2018, Mechelen, Belgium.
26. Esguerra, J.L., Krook, J., Svensson, N., van Passel, S. and van Acker, K. (2018). *The economic and environmental performance of a landfill mining project from the viewpoint of an industrial landfill owner*. Conference paper and oral presentation. 4th International Symposium on Enhanced Landfill Mining, P.T. Jones and L. Machiels (Editors). 5.-6. February 2018, Mechelen, Belgium.
27. Funari, V., Gomes, H.I., Cappelletti, M., Fedi, S., Dinelli, E., Rogerson, M., and Mayes, W.M. (2018). *Bioleaching of fly ash and bottom ash from Municipal Solid Waste Incineration for metal recovery*. Oral presentation. 13.-16. June 2018, 6th International Conference on Sustainable Solid Waste Management: Naxos Island, Greece.
28. Funari, V., Gomes, H.I., Cappelletti, M., Fedi, S., Dinelli, E., Rogerson, M., Mayes, W.M., and Rovere, M. (2018). *Bioleaching of Municipal Solid Waste Incineration residues by S- and Fe-oxidizing bacteria*. Oral presentation. 16.-21. June 2018, Resources for Future Generations 2018: Vancouver, Canada.

29. Heuss-Abbichler, S. (2018). *UNFC Evaluator Qualifications and Competent Person Requirements*. Oral presentation. 24 April 2018, Symposium on the Availability of raw materials from secondary sources - a key aspect of circular economy: Geneva, Switzerland.
30. Heuss-Abbichler, S. and Kral, U. (2018). *Cost Action MINEA (Mining the European Anthroposphere)*. Oral presentation. 8.-13. April 2018, EGU General Assembly 2018: Vienna, Austria.
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MINING the
EUROPEAN
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